

Reproducing the Experimental Results from the Paper: 'Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?'

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This paper sets out to reproduce the results from the publication: "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?". The investigation focuses on the challenges faced and key discoveries made throughout the replication process.

CCS Concepts: • **Mathematics of computing** → **Probability and statistics**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Time-series forecasting, Deep learning, Statistical methods, Reproducibility

1 Introduction

The publication "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?" [4] by Li et al. states that simple statistical methods such as linear regression and SNaive are not inferior to advanced deep learning methods like the Informer and SCINet in the context of multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting (MLSTF), particularly in achieving accurate predictions. The authors demonstrate that with input-length (n), linear regression exhibits a relatively smaller upper bound of error when comparing with deep learning methods. Additionally, the study carries out experiments that confirm that the simple methods examined outperform the mentioned non-linear models.

With the primary objective of reproducing the results presented in the provided paper, this report also aims to shed light on the reliability and availability of resources for such efforts. While mirroring the original article's workflow, the obtained results, for the most part, have been reproduced one-to-one. In the remaining cases, the values closely align with those provided by the authors. The subsequent sections delve into the experimental setup, result comparison, and address challenges encountered during the reproduction process.

2 Experimental Setup

The study focuses on the performance analysis of two simple statistical methods in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting, comparing them with the provided deep learning algorithms (see Section 2.2). The examined methods include Linear Regression that forecasts separately for each variable by applying a linear combination over historical observations and SNaive, which makes predictions based on the last same-season observations. In this analysis, both linear regression and SNaive models are considered independent variables, while MSE and MAE are treated as dependent variables and performance indicators simultaneously. To ensure a controlled environment, all data preprocessing steps outlined in the original publication were replicated (see Section 3.1). This project uses Python as the main programming tool, applying the "scikit-learn" library [7] to support the implementation of machine learning algorithms, consistent with the approach employed in the original study.

2.1 Datasets

The analysis is done using six datasets:

ETT (Electricity Transformer Temperature)[9]: 2-year electricity-transformer-temperature data from 2

Chinese counties. ETTh1 and ETTh2 represent 1-hour intervals, while ETTm1 is at a 15-minute interval.

ECL (Electricity Consuming Load)[9]: Electricity consumption data from 2011 to 2014.

WTH (Weather)[9]: Hourly weather data collected from the USA, encompassing 11 climate features.

Weather[8]: 21 meteorological indicators collected for each date in 2020, with a 10-minute sampling frequency.

ILI (Influenza-Like Illness)[8]: Weekly recorded data of influenza-like illness patients from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention of the USA, spanning 2002 to 2021.

Exchange (Exchange Rates)[8]: Daily exchange rates of eight countries from 1990 to 2016.

2.2 Related Work

The results obtained with the simple statistical methods are being compared with those from deep learning methods, which are LSTNet [3], LSTMa[1], Reformer[2], LogTrans[5], Informer [9], TCN[6] and SCINet[6], presented by Liu et al.[6] on ETT data, by Zhou et al.[9] on ECL/WTH data and by Wu et al.[8] on Weather/ILI/Exchange data.

3 Reproduction

This section delves into the reproduction process, providing insights into data configuration, model definitions, results comparison, and the challenges encountered while working with the original publication.

3.1 Data preparation and configuration

Various measures were taken to ensure consistency and comparability across diverse datasets. Z-score normalization, applied to remove unit variations in each dimension, contributed to a standardized approach for the analysis. To establish temporal alignment across datasets, a standard month duration of 30 days was used. The input size for linear regression models varied across datasets, with specific values assigned to each: ETT, ECL, WTH, Weather, ILI, and Exchange datasets had input sizes of 672, 672, 672, 672, 96, and 31, respectively.

Regarding the seasonal periods, on ETTh1 and ETTh2, the SNaive model's seasonal period is set as 24/24/168/168/672 for horizons 24/48/168/336/720. In the case of ETTm1, ECL, WTH, Weather, ILI, and Exchange datasets, the seasonal periods are defined as 96, 168, 24, 144, 52, and 1 respectively.

Finally, the training and test data were partitioned according to dataset specifics. In the ETT dataset, months 1-16 were used for training, and 17-20 for testing. In other datasets, the first 80% and last 20% were used for training and test data, respectively. The cutpoint (N_0) is applied to the training set, serving as the threshold for normalization, with values set at $0.75N$ for the ETT dataset and $0.875N$ for others.

3.2 Model Definitions

Linear Regression.

To replicate the authors results, it was essential to separately analyze each data feature, conducting a series of univariate regressions, then averaging the obtained MSE and MAE. Our regressions employed a sliding window method. The window size (input size) determined the data points number for predictions, and the prediction horizon (horizon size) indicated the forecast steps ahead. For details, see Appendix A.1.

SNaive

Our model utilizes the seasonality property of time series. The model predicts the value t_h based on the last seasonal component of the series t_{h-s} . To reproduce the authors' results, we again have to construct unidimensional (univariable) time series. For details, see Appendix A.2.

3.3 Performance Measures

In order to compare the performance of different statistical methods, mean absolute error (MAE) and mean squared error (MSE) were used.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{Hd} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \left| \frac{X_{i,j} - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} - \hat{X}_{i,j} \right|, \tag{1}$$

$$MSE = \frac{1}{Hd} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^H \left(\frac{X_{i,j} - \mu_i}{\sigma_i} - \hat{X}_{i,j} \right)^2, \tag{2}$$

where

$X_i = \{x_{i,0}, \dots, x_{i,N}\}$ with i representing the i_{th} dimension of time series

h ... horizon

H ... the number of test samples, which equals to the length of test-data minus $h - 1$

d ... dimensionality

$X_{i,j} = \{x_{i,N+j+1}, \dots, x_{i,N+j+h}\} (j = 1, \dots, H)$ for actual values

$\hat{X}_{i,j} = \{\hat{x}_{i,N+j+1}, \dots, \hat{x}_{i,N+j+h}\}$ for predicted values

σ_i ... standard deviation of X_{i1}

μ_i ... mean of X_{i1}

3.4 Result comparison

In this section, we take the results as they are presented in the original paper [4] (for more details, see Challenges 3.5) and compare them with those we have reproduced.

Table 1. Multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting results on the electricity-field datasets

Dataset		ETTh1					ETTh2					ETTm1					ECL				
Method	Metric	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	168	336	720	24	48	96	288	672	48	168	336	720	960
LSTNet [3]	MSE	1.175	1.344	1.865	2.477	1.925	2.632	3.487	1.442	1.372	2.403	1.856	1.909	2.654	1.009	1.681	0.279	0.318	0.357	0.442	0.473
	MAE	0.793	0.864	1.092	1.193	1.084	1.337	1.577	2.389	2.429	3.403	1.058	1.085	1.378	1.902	2.701	0.337	0.368	0.391	0.433	0.443
LSTMa [1]	MSE	0.536	0.616	1.058	1.152	1.682	1.049	1.331	3.987	3.276	3.711	0.621	1.392	1.339	1.740	2.736	0.388	0.492	0.778	1.528	1.343
	MAE	0.528	0.577	0.725	0.794	1.018	0.689	0.805	1.560	1.375	1.520	0.629	0.939	0.913	1.124	1.555	0.444	0.498	0.629	0.945	0.886
Reformer [2]	MSE	0.887	1.159	1.686	1.919	2.177	1.381	1.715	4.484	3.798	5.111	0.598	0.952	1.267	1.632	1.943	1.312	1.453	1.507	1.883	1.973
	MAE	0.630	0.750	0.996	1.090	1.218	1.475	1.585	1.650	1.508	1.793	0.489	0.645	0.795	0.886	1.006	0.911	0.975	0.978	1.002	1.185
LogTrans [5]	MSE	0.656	0.670	0.888	0.942	1.109	0.726	1.728	3.944	3.711	2.817	0.341	0.495	0.674	1.728	1.865	0.267	0.290	0.305	0.311	0.333
	MAE	0.600	0.611	0.766	0.766	0.843	0.638	0.944	1.573	1.587	1.356	0.495	0.527	0.674	1.656	1.721	0.366	0.382	0.395	0.397	0.413
Informer [9]	MSE	0.509	0.551	0.878	0.884	0.941	0.446	0.934	1.512	1.665	2.340	0.325	0.472	0.642	1.219	1.651	0.269	0.300	0.311	0.308	0.328
	MAE	0.523	0.563	0.722	0.753	0.768	0.523	0.733	0.996	1.035	1.209	0.440	0.537	0.626	0.871	1.002	0.351	0.376	0.385	0.385	0.406
TCN*[6]	MSE	0.467	0.478	0.652	0.787	0.927	0.424	0.594	2.355	2.396	2.572	0.210	0.219	0.243	0.724	2.136	-	-	-	-	-
	MAE	0.477	0.492	0.606	0.675	0.770	0.465	0.589	1.168	1.214	1.241	0.280	0.316	0.343	0.633	1.211	-	-	-	-	-
SCINet [6]	MSE	0.341	0.368	0.451	0.502	0.583	0.188	0.279	0.505	0.618	1.074	0.126	0.169	0.191	0.365	0.713	-	-	-	-	-
	MAE	0.379	0.395	0.457	0.497	0.560	0.288	0.358	0.504	0.560	0.761	0.229	0.274	0.291	0.415	0.604	-	-	-	-	-
SNaive Original [4]	MSE	0.424	0.465	0.656	0.683	0.650	0.266	0.322	0.578	0.567	0.550	0.168	0.168	0.188	0.225	0.282	0.212	0.212	0.212	0.228	0.267
	MAE	0.389	0.407	0.509	0.520	0.518	0.304	0.339	0.483	0.491	0.488	0.269	0.269	0.287	0.315	0.353	0.278	0.278	0.279	0.295	0.325
SNaive Reproduced	MSE	0.424	0.465	0.656	0.683	0.708	0.266	0.322	0.578	0.567	0.586	0.759	0.760	0.767	0.815	1.198	0.212	0.212	0.228	0.267	0.294
	MAE	0.389	0.407	0.509	0.520	0.557	0.304	0.339	0.483	0.491	0.515	0.603	0.603	0.606	0.616	0.715	0.278	0.279	0.295	0.325	0.344
Linear Original [4]	MSE	0.305	0.341	0.404	0.434	0.490	0.166	0.218	0.323	0.386	0.665	0.090	0.121	0.162	0.261	0.364	0.116	0.145	0.163	0.194	0.212
	MAE	0.357	0.379	0.422	0.445	0.501	0.261	0.299	0.374	0.419	0.549	0.185	0.219	0.253	0.325	0.394	0.213	0.240	0.260	0.291	0.308
Linear Reproduced	MSE	0.305	0.341	0.404	0.434	0.490	0.166	0.218	0.323	0.386	0.665	0.222	0.317	0.417	0.592	1.005	0.116	0.145	0.163	0.194	0.212
	MAE	0.357	0.3789	0.422	0.445	0.501	0.261	0.299	0.374	0.419	0.549	0.330	0.398	0.457	0.544	0.663	0.213	0.240	0.260	0.291	0.308

Table 2. Multivariate long sequence time-series forecasting results on other datasets.

Dataset		WTH					Weather				ILI				Exchange			
Method	Metric	24	48	168	336	720	96	192	336	720	24	36	48	60	96	192	336	720
LSTNet [3]	MSE	0.575	0.622	0.676	0.714	0.773	0.594	0.560	0.597	0.618	6.026	5.340	6.080	5.548	1.551	1.477	1.507	2.285
	MAE	0.507	0.553	0.585	0.607	0.643	0.587	0.565	0.587	0.599	1.770	1.668	1.787	1.720	1.058	1.028	1.031	1.243
Reformer [2]	MSE	0.583	0.633	1.228	1.770	2.548	0.689	0.752	0.639	1.130	4.400	4.783	4.832	4.882	1.065	1.188	1.357	1.510
	MAE	0.497	0.556	0.763	0.997	1.407	0.596	0.638	0.596	0.792	1.382	1.448	1.465	1.483	0.829	0.906	0.976	1.016
LogTrans [5]	MSE	0.365	0.496	0.649	0.666	0.741	0.458	0.658	0.797	0.869	4.480	4.799	4.800	5.278	0.968	1.040	1.659	1.941
	MAE	0.405	0.485	0.573	0.584	0.611	0.490	0.589	0.652	0.675	1.444	1.467	1.468	1.560	0.812	0.851	1.081	1.127
Informer [9]	MSE	0.355	0.471	0.613	0.626	0.680	0.300	0.598	0.578	1.059	5.767	4.755	4.763	5.264	0.847	1.204	1.672	2.478
	MAE	0.383	0.456	0.544	0.548	0.569	0.384	0.544	0.523	0.741	1.677	1.467	1.469	1.564	0.752	0.895	1.036	1.310
Autoformer [8]	MSE	-	-	-	-	-	0.266	0.307	0.359	0.419	3.484	3.103	2.669	2.770	0.197	0.300	0.509	1.447
	MAE	-	-	-	-	-	0.336	0.367	0.395	0.428	1.287	1.148	1.085	1.125	0.323	0.369	0.524	0.941
SNaive Original [4]	MSE	0.599	0.698	0.848	0.908	0.960	0.317	0.343	0.383	0.443	2.564	2.266	2.142	1.917	0.081	0.167	0.306	0.810
	MAE	0.468	0.525	0.608	0.642	0.674	0.288	0.305	0.331	0.370	1.004	0.957	0.941	0.939	0.196	0.289	0.398	0.676
SNaive Reproduced	MSE	0.599	0.698	0.848	0.908	0.960	0.317	0.343	0.383	0.443	2.564	2.266	2.142	1.917	0.081	0.167	0.306	0.810
	MAE	0.468	0.525	0.608	0.642	0.674	0.288	0.305	0.331	0.370	1.004	0.957	0.941	0.939	0.196	0.289	0.398	0.676
Linear Original [4]	MSE	0.323	0.391	0.500	0.543	0.602	0.139	0.181	0.229	0.295	2.168	2.233	2.277	2.353	0.082	0.166	0.282	0.576
	MAE	0.361	0.420	0.504	0.534	0.572	0.200	0.244	0.288	0.341	0.97	1.015	1.040	1.067	0.200	0.292	0.395	0.604
Linear Reproduced	MSE	0.318	0.387	0.497	0.542	0.603	0.144	0.188	0.240	0.312	2.198	2.282	2.321	2.395	0.106	0.210	0.359	0.734
	MAE	0.361	0.421	0.505	0.536	0.575	0.207	0.254	0.299	0.356	0.976	1.025	1.049	1.076	0.226	0.328	0.443	0.676

We observe the following: for ETTh1 and ETTh2 datasets, the reproduction is perfect except for the horizon of 720 for SNaive, where metric values are slightly worse (higher), but not dramatically.

The ECL dataset situation is almost similar: Reproduced SNaive slightly differs for the worse, now not only for the horizon of 720 but also for 336 and 960.

For the WTH, Weather, ILI, and Exchange datasets, SNaive matches perfectly. The Linear results here slightly differs, and in the case of MSE for WTH, reproduced version shows even better values (for all horizons, except for 720).

However, the ETTm1 dataset presents a different picture, with reproduced results mostly significantly worse, up to four times, in both SNaive and Linear.

3.5 Challenges

In the process of our work, we encountered the following difficulties: The authors did not provide a clear description of the model, particularly, it appears that they most likely constructed a univariate model for each dimension, which was not explicitly stated. They did not precisely describe how the metrics were calculated, leaving room for interpretation. Additionally, the exact percentage used for standardization was not clarified. Lastly, it seems they assumed, but did not explicitly state, that the train-test split considers a month to be 30 days long, which also leads to different results.

Since the article is essentially dedicated to comparing the results of the Simpler Statistical Methods with more complex Statistical and Deep Learning Methods, it is extremely important how the authors of the article present other people's data, taken from different sources.

The results upon which the authors of the article base their conclusions are presented in Tables 1, 2, and 3. They clearly state where they obtained other people's results of statistical and deep learning methods. However, when attempting to find these values in the corresponding sources, we fail.

After our investigation, we located the original papers results of *TCN† series for the ETT dataset in an older version of [6]. The remaining data for the ETT, ECL, and WTH datasets were found in the 2020 version of [9]. For the Weather, ILI, and Exchange datasets, the required numbers were indeed present in the article [8], as referenced by the authors. The only results we were unable to confirm were for SCINet algorithm on the ETT dataset.

4 Conclusion

In this report, we attempted to reproduce the experimental results from the paper "Do Simpler Statistical Methods Perform Better in Multivariate Long Sequence Time-Series Forecasting?" by demonstrating that linear regression and SNaive exhibit performance comparable to state-of-the-art deep learning methods in minimizing prediction errors for MLSTF. Despite challenges in acquiring code and data, and some confusion surrounding the referenced articles, it was possible to replicate the workflow and obtain results similar with those presented in the given publication. Notably, SNaive demonstrated one-to-one results for 4 out of 6 datasets examined, while for the remaining datasets, both SNaive and linear regression exhibited values closely resembling those presented in the original study.

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A Appendix

A.1 Linear Regression: Illustration

H=2, N=3

H represents the horizon or the number of future time steps we are predicting, and N represents the number of past time steps (or features) used to make the prediction.

The explicit formula for our regression is given by:

$$\hat{Y}_i = \alpha_{11} \cdot D_i + \alpha_{12} \cdot D_{i+1} + \alpha_{13} \cdot D_{i+2},$$

$$\hat{Y}_{i+1} = \alpha_{21} \cdot D_i + \alpha_{22} \cdot D_{i+1} + \alpha_{23} \cdot D_{i+2}.$$

A.2 SNaive: Illustration

H=2, Season=4

H represents the horizon or the number of future time steps we are predicting, and Season represents the length of a time-period where similar data is expected again. The prediction uses the values from the last season.